

Elucidating hidden slime mold diversity in Southeast Asia: A review of potential methods

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Abstract: Slime mold data in Southeast Asia heavily relies on culture-dependent methods and field-collected sporocarps to assess their diversity in distinct terrestrial ecosystems. This dependence creates a bias against species that do not form sporocarps. Plasmodia do not always generate reproductive structures in moist chambers, and amoebae cannot be cultured directly from soil. Additionally, based on previous studies, investigations have proposed a paradigm of reverse pattern in slime mold diversity in which temperate regions are more diverse than the tropics. However, this is challenged by more studies in the tropics, showing that the pattern is more of an effort bias than an actual biological pattern. Despite the notion that molecular methods hold great potential in recording diversity, more recent sporocarp-based research has challenged such a paradigm. Hence, methods need to be polyphasic to fully understand the sizeable unknown gap of hidden biodiversity in the terrestrial ecosystem. This review tackles the opportunities and challenges of elucidating hidden slime mold diversity in the tropical Southeast Asian region.

Keywords: barcoding, eDNA, field surveys, moist chambers, NGS, plasmodia

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Introduction

Slime molds belong to the superkingdom Amoebozoa – a large group of heterotrophic protists (Adl et al. 2012) consisting of amoeba-like organisms throughout their life cycle (Simpson et al. 2017). In this classification, many lineages develop sporocarps or fruiting bodies for spore dispersal. Olive (1975) established a classical taxon within the superkingdom that contains three main groups dubbed as the "true slime molds" – the taxon Eumycetozoa – classically grouping fruiting amoeboid organisms. This taxon was created to include three groups of sporocarpic organisms: the myxomycetes, a monophyletic group of plasmodial slime molds whose fruiting bodies are composed of spores and non-cellular stalks; the dictyostelids, a monophyletic group of cellular slime molds whose feeding stages are pseudoplasmodia and cellular stalks; and the protostelioid amoebae (formerly known as the Protostelids), a paraphyletic assemblage of plasmodial mycetozoans, forming fruiting bodies with a single or a few terminal spores and non-cellular stalk (Spiegel 1991; Leontyev and Schnittler 2017; Spiegel et al. 2017).

Some unifying characteristics can be observed in the Eumycetozoa as described by Olive and other researchers (Olive 1975; Adl et al. 2012; Spiegel et al. 2017). Among these are the presence of amoeboid trophic cells with distinct sharp sub-pseudopodia, the ability to produce stalked, spore-bearing fruiting bodies (absent in some myxomycete species), and the presence of mitochondria with tubular cristae. Since protostelioid amoebae are paraphyletic, initial phylogenetic studies revealed that only one group, the Protosporangiida, is closely related to myxomycetes and dictyostelids (Baldauf and Doolittle 1997; Adl et al. 2012).

Overview of Eumycetozoan Ecology and Distribution

Protostelioid amoebae, dictyostelids, and myxomycetes are eukaryotic and phagotrophic predators feeding on bacteria and fungi on decaying substrates and soil (Cavender 2013; Novozhilov et al. 2017a; Spiegel et al. 2017), often ubiquitous across different terrestrial ecosystems (Stephenson et al. 1999). The ecology and global distribution associated with the diversity of forms display a broad level of variation.

Protostelioid amoebae have been observed across different terrestrial habitats ranging from temperate mountain ranges (Shadwick et al. 2009) to tropical forests (Stephenson et al. 1999; Moore and Spiegel 2000; Moore and Stephenson 2003) across different continents (Ndiritu et al. 2009). Geographic isolation does not seem to be a limitation for their potential dispersal (Spiegel et al. 2017) since some species are found in major and remote islands in the Pacific region (Olive 1975), such as subantarctic Macquarie Island (Spiegel and Stephenson 2000). Generally, species richness appears to follow an increasing pattern from the tropics to the temperate regions, decreasing again at higher latitudes (Spiegel et al. 2017). However, there is no empirical data from a standard representative experimental design demonstrating the latter, likely due to its cost and complexity. As such, the observed pattern has been inferred from several studies, originally designed for a wide variety of goals. Elevation also poses a negative impact on species assemblages (Ndiritu et al. 2009). Collections from 3000 meters above sea level rarely yield protostelioid amoebae (Spiegel et al. 2017). Interestingly, there is no present explanation for this phenomenon. Aquatic environments are also reported as potential habitats for protostelids (Lindley et al. 2007; Tesmer and Schnittler 2009).

Dictyostelid amoebae can also be recorded in various terrestrial habitats. Temperate deciduous forests are the best-studied biomes, but high diversity patterns can be found in tropical and subtropical environments (Swanson et al. 1999). Cavender et al. (1993) have also investigated their presence in tropical environments influenced by agricultural disturbances. Despite the richness associated with tropical and subtropical regions, the density of dictyostelids in forest soils is comparatively low, having no clear distribution pattern ever been mentioned (Swanson et al. 1999). Swanson et al. (1999), however, demonstrated a considerable gap of dictyostelid collections from the Southern Hemisphere. Despite those shortcomings, a downward trend in species diversity has been observed from the Northern to the Southern Hemisphere. However, one must consider that dictyostelids are understudied in the Southern Hemisphere, with recent discoveries (Wrigley de Basanta et al. 2013; Perrigo et al. 2020) offering new insights to distribution. Much like the protostelids and other terrestrial organisms, there is an increase in diversity approaching the equator (Cavender 1973; Cavender 2013). It is speculated that canopy soils are more favorable microhabitats than ground soils (Stephenson and Landolt 1998, 2011), but this notion requires more intensive sampling efforts to come into fruition.

Lastly, myxomycetes are the most extensively studied in terms of ecology, distribution, and biogeography. This can be attributed to the common occurrence of sporocarps wherever there is sufficient decaying organic matter, provided with adequate moisture and temperature (Ko et al. 2011). Some notable collecting habitats are rotting logs in forests or forested areas and patches of decaying leaf litter, tree barks, woody vines, and herbivorous dung, to name a few (Keller et al. 2017). Plant inflorescences (i.e., *Heliconia* and *Costus*) are also suitable microhabitats for myxomycetes (Schnittler and Stephenson 2002). The diversity of tropical myxomycetes seems to defy the conventional notion of increasing species richness with decreasing latitude (Schnittler et al. 2017a), where tropical regions steer towards lower species richness compared to temperate areas. This reflects on the extensive work previously done in temperate regions. Unlike the protostelids and dictyostelids, there appears to be a reverse pattern for myxomycetes. In contrast to protostelids, whose geographic isolations does not seem to be a limitation for their dispersal, myxomycetes tend to follow the protist biogeography hypothesis of 'moderate endemism' (Dagamac et al. 2017a) as opposed to the 'everything is everywhere' hypothesis (Aguilar et al. 2014). Dagamac et al. (2017b) further discussed that myxomycetes are not ubiquitous, provided by the evidence of geographically restricted morphospecies and differences in myxomycete assemblages in the Neotropics and Paleotropics.

The Concept of Hidden Diversity

Documentation of microorganisms remains largely incomplete due to the complexity associated with their sampling and detection. This is partially due to their small size, their high reproductive dynamics and dispersal capacities, overall abundance, and certain unique aspects of their life cycles (Fiore-Donno et al. 2010; Novozhilov et al. 2017a). In the case of myxomycetes, studies are focused well on their synecology, analyzing the occurrence of sporocarps in relation to environmental gradients (Novozhilov et al. 2017a). Furthermore, the current species concept of slime molds is based almost completely upon characterization of morphological features of the sporocarps, and their spores (Cavender 2013; Novozhilov et al. 2017a; Spiegel et al. 2017) since trophic stages (amoeboflagellates and plasmodia/pseudoplasmodia) display little for taxonomic purposes. Fruiting bodies or sporocarps are usually the only way to differentiate species, providing a basic unit for taxonomic classification because they are extractable, identifiable, and quantifiable. Hence, these characteristic morphological features are commonly employed in field observations, moist chamber techniques, and primary isolation plates.

However, these traditional methods of taxonomic characterization do not account for the effects of their complex life cycles, nor do they reveal reproductive isolation within morphospecies (Walker and Stephenson 2016). In the case of myxomycetes, only approximately 60% of all morphospecies can be detected in the field using classical approaches (Novozhilov et al. 2017a). For 200 years, research on myxomycetes centered around sporocarps, allowing a broad application of a morphological species concept (Schnittler and Kirschner 2017). This leaves some ubiquitous species undetected, such as those who have lost the ability to mate and form fruiting bodies (Fiore-Donno et al. 2010). Consequently, the modern challenge of biodiversity studies is to detect the previously undetectable. This approach suggests that studies utilizing traditional methods grossly underestimate myxomycetes in the field (Fiore-Donno et al. 2016). Small, inconspicuous, and non-fruiting species under suboptimum levels remain invisible. One paper (Schnittler et al. 2017a) suggested that, from a biodiversity point of view, we are merely looking at the "tip of the iceberg" – only seeing populations successfully fruiting in optimal conditions. Soil microbial community structures reveal that Mycetozoans are the most abundant protist group in soils (Urich et al.

2008). Ruling out that non-fruiting strains of slime molds existing in nature is quite unlikely, one must assume that slime molds are much more distributed than indicated by fruiting records alone (Schnittler et al. 2017a). Plasmodia that do not fruit and the difficulty of culturing amoebae from soil samples prove to be problematic.

To address the challenge of hidden diversity in myxomycetes and other Amoebozoans (e.g. the issue of non-fruiting species), metacommunity analysis and other molecular-based methods are often employed (Kamono and Fukui 2006; Urich et al. 2008; Kamono et al. 2013; Shchepin et al. 2019a). Spiegel et al. (2017) also suggested that future work on protostelioid amoebae should also include environmental sequencing. It may yield further details on their distribution, biogeography, and ecology, especially those not observed to form sporocarps.

Presently, slime mold research (specifically for myxomycetes and dictyostelids) in Southeast Asia heavily relies on conventional methods to assess ecological patterns of occurrence and distribution. Modern molecular techniques are either scarce or follow a slow, gradual increase (Dagamac and dela Cruz 2019). This places the tropical Southeast Asian region on the tip of the iceberg regarding advancements in slime mold research.

One may cast doubt on the true diversity of slime molds that have been reported in the Philippines (e.g., Macabago et al. 2017, Pecundo et al. 2017, Bernardo et al. 2018), Thailand (Tran et al. 2006; Tran et al. 2008), Vietnam (e.g., Tran et al. 2014, Nguyen et al. 2019, Redeña-Santos et al. 2018, Novozhilov et al. 2020), Singapore (Rosing et al. 2011), and Laos (Ko et al. 2012), to name a few, given the conundrum of hidden diversity. Although, despite the limitations of conventional methods, the region has seen a steady increase in slime molds research over the past 20 years. Nonetheless, state-of-the-art techniques such as DNA barcoding (Schnittler et al. 2017b) and next-generation sequencing (Shchepin et al. 2019b) may represent a viable path for future endeavors. Hence, this review will address some perspectives in applying modern methods to study Southeast Asian slime molds.

Current Status on the Methods Used in Southeast Asian Slime Mold Studies

Field Surveys

Field collections employ the direct extraction of fruiting bodies from the fields. Novozhilov et al. (2017a) noted that productive field surveys are usually observed during rainy seasons. This has been supported by phenological studies conducted by Tran et al. (2008) across five study sites in northern Thailand, recovering 62 species in the rainy season yet only two species during the dry season. However, recent phenological studies in the Neotropics suggest that myxomycete sporocarps are virtually always present yet varies temporally in species assemblages (Rojas et al. 2021a). Furthermore, field-based surveys must often account for seasonal and environmental flux to avoid artifacts related to phenological differences in sporulation activity (Novozhilov et al. 2017b). Rojas and his colleagues further suggest that remaining ecological effects can be associated with more specific factors such as ecosystem structure, substrate quality and availability, biotic interactions, and even climate change.

Collected fruiting bodies are immediately placed in compartmentalized cardboard collecting boxes and air-dried for several days (Novozhilov et al. 2018; Pecundo et al. 2020). This method is often employed in collecting myxomycetes in the field since their fruiting bodies are much more hardy

compared to protosteloid amoebae and dictyostelids. Additionally, the size of the latter two is much smaller compared to the former. However, some macroscopic protosteloid amoebae can be directly collected in the field (e.g., *Ceratiomyxa*) (Dagamac et al. 2015a). Collected field specimens are eventually glued on herbarium trays and placed inside herbarium matchboxes for permanent storage.

Some examples of studies using this collecting methodology and carried out in the archipelagic islands of the Philippines include the following. Dagamac et al. (2015b) employed a direct collection of fruiting bodies in their survey of different forest types in Puerto Galera, Oriental Mindoro. Out of the 42 species that occurred in their study area (both field collections and moist chamber cultures), 25 were present in their field sampling. Notable species such as *Lycogala epidendrum*, *Lycogala exiguum*, *Hemitrichia calyculata*, *Diderma effusum*, *Physarum pusillum*, *Physarum pulcherrimum*, *Physarum roseum*, *Physarum superbum*, *Craterium aureum*, and *Craterium leucocephalum* were exclusively found in the field and were not observed in moist chamber cultures. The macroscopic protosteloid amoebae *Ceratiomyxa fruticulosa* was also collected exclusively in the field.

Additionally, in a survey in lower montane forests and agricultural plantations in Negros Occidental, Alfaro et al. (2014) noted 193 records; 42 were fruiting body records from the field. The study also emphasized that no field specimens were observed in agricultural plantations. Species collected exclusively in the field and were not isolated in moist chamber cultures were *Arcyria denudata*, *Craterium leucophaeum* var. *cylindricum*, *Hemitrichia calyculata*, *Cribraria cancellata*, *Cribraria microcarpa*, *Physarum melleum*, *Comatrachia nigra*, *Didymium squamolosum*, *Hemitrichia serpula*, *Physarum bogoriense*, *Physarum compressum*, *Physarum nucleatum*, and *Trichia decipiens*. Other notable studies that employed field collection are those conducted in a Tropical Karst Forest, Quezon Province [7 out of 137 records (Dagamac et al. 2015a)], and the Bicol Peninsula [33 out of 746 records (Dagamac et al. 2017c)]. These field surveys and the fieldwork surveys conducted on lowland (Novozhilov et al. 2017b) and highland (Novozhilov et al. 2020) tropical forests of Southern Vietnam and highland forests of Thailand (Ko et al. 2010) support the moderate species endemism (Dagamac et al. 2017b) of myxomycetes in the region.

Methods Used for Dictyostelid and Myxomycete Surveys

The moist chamber technique was first utilized and described by (Gilbert and Martin 1933), studying myxomycetes in the bark of living trees. Later on, Stephenson and Stempen (1994) revisited the method and optimized it – becoming the standard method in culturing myxomycetes using moist chambers to date. In fact, almost all of the studies regarding myxomycetes here in the region use the moist chamber technique due to its simplicity and effectiveness in recovering myxomycete species in the field. Additionally, this technique is adequate to reflect the diversity of myxomycetes in a particular habitat or site (Novozhilov et al. 2000). Hence, this technique can supplement the information gathered from specimens that have successfully fruited in field collections and surveys under natural conditions (Stephenson and Stempen 1994; Novozhilov et al. 2017a).

This technique usually requires only Petri dishes, filter paper, and a dissecting microscope. One advantage of this method is that it does not need sterile conditions to provide meaningful results and it is easily modifiable to suit the researcher's needs (Novozhilov et al. 2017a). An example is the use of toilet paper instead of filter paper when the latter is not available (Dagamac et al. 2010; Dagamac et al. 2017c; Redeña-Santos et al. 2017; Buisan et al. 2019, 2020). Plastic containers (like those used in food products) are also a suitable replacement for Petri dishes. Substrates are then collected from the field and placed in

small paper bags, transported to the laboratory, and allowed to air-dry for an ample amount of time (e.g., 1-2 weeks, depending on the moisture content of the substrates). A typical 1-10 gram dry substrate material or cut postage-stamp-sized pieces of the substrate are placed in the moist chamber lined with filter paper. Water is added to submerge the substrates for 24 hours, at which the pH is measured and the excess water is decanted. The monitoring schedule and total duration vary among studies. Generally, moist chambers are kept under diffuse lighting at room temperature for 8 to 12 weeks. When fruiting bodies are observed, they are collected and preserved in the same manner as specimens from field collections.

However, given the simplicity of this technique, some limitations are also eminent. Since this method employs unnatural conditions, it may produce species records from dormant stages that would not or very rarely have formed fruiting bodies under natural conditions (Novozhilov et al. 2017b). In addition to the unnatural conditions set by the moist chamber technique, one obvious limitation of the method is that it can be time-consuming. Despite the method's flexibility for biodiversity purposes, it has its drawbacks for any study that requires standardization. A study by Rojas et al. (2021b) saw differences in observed values of diversity indices by synchronously conducting moist chamber experiments in two laboratories 30 km apart. The study saw the influence of various variables that are not commonly considered in the general application of the protocol. This prompts future works on an optimized version of the method leading to standardized protocols.

Dictyostelids, on the other hand, use different methods. Compared to the moist chamber technique, isolation of dictyostelids require a sterile work environment. So far, in the region, very little progress has been made with studies of dictyostelids, where most taxonomical approaches are done morphologically (Dagamac and dela Cruz 2019). Recent species listing and surveys in the Philippines were only carried out in Subic Bay, Zambales (dela Cruz et al. 2011) and Lubang Island, Occidental Mindoro (Yulo and dela Cruz 2011, 2012). On these past surveys, the protocol by Cavender and Raper (1965) was usually followed. Soil suspensions are often employed and transferred to buffered Hay Infusion Agar plates amended with bacteria (usually *Escherichia coli*) as a food source.

Protostelid Studies in Southeast Asia: What's in it for us?

The whole idea of studying protostelioid amoebae is still in its infancy for the Southeast Asian region. Although protostelioid amoebae have been published before in the reports of Reynolds (1981) in Southeast Asia, these are either just records or occurrences investigated alongside myxomycetes. However, only one species, *Ceratiomyxa fruticolosa*, has ever been extensively recorded in the region. This species was previously classified under myxomycetes but is now categorized under the protostelioid amoebae (Olive 1970, 1975). Nevertheless, protostelioid amoebae are still reported in several myxomycete ecological surveys in Southeast Asia (e.g., dela Cruz et al. 2010, Alfaro et al. 2014, Tran et al. 2014, Dagamac et al. 2015a) either recorded directly from the field or growing in moist chamber cultures.

Protostelioid amoebae research is non-active in the Southeast Asian region. This is not surprising since these organisms are treated as an obscure group of relatively little to no economic importance (Spiegel et al. 2017). However, several papers have previously suggested the use of protostelioid amoebae for the study of cell motility and the evolution of cell motility systems (Spiegel 1981), as a model for non-muscle cellular contractile systems (Spiegel et al. 1979), and as biocontrol for soil microbial populations that are potentially pathogenic (Feest 1987). More work is required to further elucidate the practical importance of protostelioid amoebae without falling into any type of business-modeled applied research.

Opportunities of Using Modern Molecular Methods in Slime Mold Studies

To date, slime mold researchers working on biodiversity matters face a dilemma over the existence of two alternative species concept: the practicality of the morphological species concept and the meaningfulness of the biological species concept (Collins 1979; Clark 1995). The former only provides a limited taxonomic resolution while the latter is harder to implement (Schnittler et al. 2017b), and its applicability in developing areas of the world is limited. Hence, modern molecular approaches offer alternative means to study and further reveal the complexity of slime molds.

One promising molecular approach being used by myxomycete researchers is barcoding, or the utilization of molecular markers in DNA to differentiate and identify species. In Southeast Asia, this particular method has been applied to phylogeographic studies that addressed the concept of biospecies on certain myxomycete species such as *Hemitrichia serpula* (Dagamac et al. 2017a) and *Diderma hemisphaericum* (Almadrones-Reyes et al. 2019). Denaturing gradient gel electrophoresis (DGGE) fingerprinting was also applied by Ko et al. (2009) in northern Thailand to assess myxomycete molecular diversity from environmental samples. The latter method had successfully revealed several operational taxonomic units (OTUs) from decaying wood and forest floor litter.

Moreover, barcoding has also been used to confirm the occurrence of a new species of *Diderma* found in Vietnam (Novozhilov et al. 2019). DNA barcoding offers an alternative to detect microorganisms that cannot be cultured in the laboratory (Epstein 2013). This method is seen as the most advanced in the field of molecular approaches applied to biodiversity. Schnittler et al. (2020) have developed a very quick and cheap protocol for the efficient barcoding of myxomycete sporocarps, which requires less than 1000 spores, can be implemented with the use of an aseptic needle, works without using expensive commercial kits, and is already optimized for the use of 96-well PCR plates throughout the process. This method has the potential of helping myxomycete researchers interested in biodiversity issues in Southeast Asia to increase the number of molecular sequences of myxomycetes in the region, an important task to understand variability and study molecular evolution of taxa. Such an approach can also provide a scientific basis to evaluate the ecological patterns of occurrence of Southeast Asian myxomycetes that have, thus far, heavily relied on sporocarp data.

The ribosomal small subunit (SSU) RNA gene is currently the most widely used marker for the molecular analysis of slime molds since it is an extremely slow-evolving gene (Walker et al. 2017). Additionally, molecular barcoding using SSU rRNA has become extremely popular among protistologists (Guillou et al. 2013) and proving to be a highly variable marker, containing a large number of group I introns of various lengths (Shadwick LL et al. 2009; Fiore-Donno et al. 2010; Fiore-Donno et al. 2012; Nandipati et al. 2012; Walker et al. 2017; Perrigo et al. 2020). The use of SSU rRNA successfully reconstructed and revised the molecular phylogeny of dictyostelids and easily unraveled underlying mechanisms (Schaap et al. 2006). Perrigo et al. (2013) also used this marker to confirm the identity of dictyostelid species in high altitude habitats in Northern Sweden.

Another promising application of this marker is its use to identify myxomycetes. Many plasmodia appearing in moist chamber cultures do not yield sporocarps and are therefore unidentifiable. However, Shchepin et al. (2017) has successfully utilized DNA barcoding in plasmodia and sclerotia of myxomycetes appearing in moist chambers. The first ca. 600 bp of the 18S rRNA gene was successfully amplified in a handful of sclerotia and plasmodia samples collected in Vietnam and Russia, suggesting the effectivity of the method to complement classical approaches. One disadvantage of the method is that

researchers also obtain a number of "noisy" sequences from the microorganisms inside the vacuoles of the actively feeding vegetative structure when used in plasmodia. Also, it is less convenient to handle and is prone to DNA degradation. Moreover, the genetic barcoding of many dark-spored myxomycetes conducted by Borg Dahl et al. (2018a) suggested a sequence similarity threshold for species identification which is very helpful for NGS (next-generation sequencing) studies conducted in many novel environments (Borg Dahl et al. 2018b; Shchepin et al. 2019a, 2019b).

The generation of decisive statements and identification through the use of molecular data do pose additional limitations. Using a set empirical criterion to delimit species may result in an overestimation of biodiversity calculations (Zhang et al. 2017) and spatial scaling patterns (Tu 2020). Moreover, given the increase in appetite to interpreting these kinds of data, researcher's should work quickly towards criteria that allow for the apparent separation of approaches appropriate for surveillance from those in general biodiversity monitoring contexts (Darling et al. 2020)

Conclusions and Recommendations

The study of slime molds has taken place since the 18th century. In the Southeast Asian region, slime mold scientists and enthusiasts have been studying the organisms for more than 50 years. Over time, the most employed methods for studying slime mold diversity have been field surveys and in vitro isolation procedures that utilize artificial conditions, leading to the likely underestimation of slime mold biodiversity. For this reason, the concept of the "tip of the iceberg", as applied to biodiversity studies, also affects Southeast Asian myxomycete research. The concept of hidden diversity is no stranger to researchers who work with these organisms. Thus, the mixed-use of classical and modern approaches seems to be the future of biodiversity-related research. As part of this working strategy, a polyphasic approach is necessary to study the ecological patterns of occurrence of slime molds of Southeast Asia since one method may not completely elucidate the current dilemma. Molecular and modern methods alone will not define a species and may be inadequate approaches for questions outside of taxonomy and biodiversity, while classical techniques often undervalue the species concept.

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